

Automatic Handling of Dry Carbon Fabrics and Prepregs

Dr.-Ing. Hilmar APMANN
PREMIUM AEROTEC
Riesweg 151-155
D-26316 Varel, Germany
hilmar.apmann@premium-aerotec.com

SUMMARY

The automated handling of dry fabrics and prepreg material is validated. Several systems can handle different sorts of CFRP-materials with a very high level of repeatability and matured systems being independent of manual processes. Both dry fabrics and prepreg material can be handled and draped by specially designed end-effectors.

Keywords: Automation, CFRP, Handling, Draping, Positioning

INTRODUCTION

Due to the demands arising from materials and higher output-rates in aircraft production the aspect of automated handling of CFRP-material becomes more and more important. As a consequence the development of such systems for i.e. CFRP-frame and -stringer production is on focus for the aircraft industry. To achieve these goals, the Premium AEROTEC Centre of Production Systems realized systems for automated handling of dry CFRP-material, window surround reinforcements as well as stringer and frame preforms and even more made by prepreg material.

HANDLING OF DRY CFRP-MATERIAL

At a first step a simple handling devices was developed to handle dry CFRP-material with a pneumatic supported end-effector. This end-effector is made for handling single material layers without any helping devices like paper in between the CFRP-layers. The system enables a single manipulation and positioning of this dry CFRP-material with an automatic device.

The end-effector is equipped with 10 suction cups arranged in a circle . The handled material was multi axial dry fabric with $+45^\circ$ and -45° layers. The suction cups were modified and further developed. This provides the almost contact less handling of extremely sensitive materials and workpieces. Moreover air permeable material like dry fabrics can also be handled by this system, which leads to no damages of the material by the use of this end-effector (see figure 1)

During the tests we made with the end-effector, a maximum speed of $v = 2$ m/s in all directions was used for transportation of the dry fabric. The following test results have been generated after 100 test cycles:

- Fully automated handling of the dry fabric with the developed end-effector assisted by a KUKA-robot.
- No damages the dry fabric material can be recognized
- Moving speed of maximum $v = 2 \text{ m/s}$ were used.
- After the 100 test cycles there were no displacements and no torsions or twisting of the material plies during the test procedures
- No unallowable deformation of the material during the tests.

Figure 1 : End-effector with dry CFRP-Material

HANDLING OF PREPREG-MATERIAL

For the handling of CFRP-window frame reinforcements, which consist of polar-prepreg-patches, the pneumatic handling device developed in the first place was further improved and adapted to a conventional robot system. This system was developed for positioning prepreg preforms on a fuselage shell. The process of picking the preform from the preparing station and positioning on the fuselage shell is completely automated with the support of an optical sensor system and functions without interference of manual work-force (see figure 2)

The used end-effector started with the same configuration as the end-effector handling the dry fabrics (described before) was equipped with 10 circular arranged suction cups, activated by valve cluster with a retention force of 4 N each and an air consumption of 100 l/min each. The handled material was polar patches for window area reinforcement with a fibre area weight of about 290 g/m^2 and 0° circumferential fibre direction.

The suction cups were modified and further developed. This provides the almost contact less handling of extremely sensitive materials and workpieces.

Figure 2: First end-effector for handling prepreg material

During the tests for laying up the window reinforcement preregs at an aircraft shell with a movement-speed of about $v = 0.4$ m/s were successful. Further positioning tests we made with the end-effector, at a maximum speed of $v = 2$ m/s in all directions were used for transportation operations of the preregs. The following test results have been generated after 100 test cycles:

- Fully automated handling of the dry fabric with the developed end-effector assisted by a KUKA-robot.
- No damages of the prepreg material were recognized
- Moving speed of maximum $v = 2$ m/s and average speed of $v = 0.6$ m/s were used.
- After the 100 test cycles there were displacements of about 1 mm and torsions or twisting of max. 2° of the material plies during the test procedures.
- No unallowable deformation of the material during the tests.

After further development aimed at better handling of prepreg material an end-effector was generated with the support of an automated visual control system, a force measurement device and a special plastic foam assisted carrying device at the end effector. The elements of the end effector can be seen in the following figure 3 .

Figure 3: Further developed end-effector for handling of prepreg material

With the foam assisted a force controlled and fully area lay-up of the Prepreg-preform can be provided. Thus the Prepreg-preform can be pressed onto the simulated panel with full contact area between prepreg and panel. Different foams were tested and compared with regard to the adaptability to the specific lay-up-process and the inter-reaction between Prepreg-material and manipulator.

During validation, two different variants of the lay-up process were investigated determined by the configuration of the end-effector. The draping foam can be shaped in concave and also in convex manner. As a consequence, the draping and lay-up process is very different.

With the concave draping shape, the prepreg-preform can be laid-up merely from one direction, due to the pre-configured end-effector. The end-effector has the same shape as the panel, on which the prepreg-material is to be placed. Thus the positioning of the material can be achieved by a 3-axis-based system, which is available in many cases in automatic manufacturing systems.

The end-effector with the convex shape of the draping manipulator has to be handled by a 6-axis-robot system, because the prepreg-preform has to be picked-up with a rolling motion from a flat table and the Prepreg-material has to be rolled up onto the contour following a complex curve. The main advantage of the convex system is the flexibility. The end-effector can position the Prepreg-material onto almost every 3-D-contour (see figure 4).

In addition the end-effector is equipped with a sensor system for force measurement for monitoring the pick-up and lay-up-process and also with a black-/white CCD-camera-system for ensuring correct positioning of the prepreg-material on the contour.

Figure 4: Different shapes of end-effector for draping geometrically configured prepreg-material

HANDLING OF CFRP-STRINGER

As a further step the automated handling of CFRP-stringer prepreg material was developed with the help of an industrial robot. The main goals to fulfil were the extraction of the stringer preform from the material carpet at the tape-layer-machine. After extraction the positioning of the preform inside the preform tooling and additionally in the curing-tool without any damages at the material were further goals to reach. This entire process chain of automated handling and positioning of CFRP-stringer material was developed.

DEFORMATION PROCESS

For the deformation process of the stringer preform material an end-effector with vacuum suction cups was developed. This end-effector was also equipped with an force-torque-measurement device and with plastic foam material for holding down the prepreg material surrounding the pre-cut stringer preform. The following figure 5 shows the end-effector.

The fully automated deformation process can only be facilitated when using the plastic foams for holding down the surrounding material. In order not to damage the laminate the end-effector has used a force-torque measurement device with preset maximum force level for handling the laminate. The end-effector is guided by an industrial robot programmed on a point-to-point-basis. Further movement was generated with the help of the installed sensors.

During the tests the results show that the use of the holding down devices for the extraction process of prepreg material is necessary to ensure an automated process with industrial relevance. In addition the use of a force-torque measurement device is essential for a damage-free handling of the material in both cases, the extraction and

positioning on a table as well as in a tooling. The movement of the material within the end-effector can be about $v = 1.5$ m/s at maximum.

Figure 5: end-effector for extraction of stringer preforms

POSITIONING INTO PREFORM TOOLING

As the second step for the handling of stringer material the extraction of the stringer preforms and their positioning in the preform tooling was developed. The end-effector and the pre-positioning is shown in picture 6.

Figure 6: Pre-positioning of the end-effector with the stringer laminate

For the positioning of the stringer laminate in the preform tooling almost the same end-effector was used as for the extraction of the laminate. The fully automated positioning of the laminate can only be realized by support of an industrial robot and a force measurement device, which manipulates the control of the robot in a smooth way. The laminate can be driven to a mechanical end stop inside the tooling. After reaching a

maximum force level at the end stop the laminate can be tracked into the tooling across the entire length. Summarised this process can provide a non damaging position of the laminate in the tooling.

Basis of this procedure is the setting of the process parameters while using the vacuum cups, moving the end-effector with the laminate and resorting to an automated process supported by a force measurement device.

LAY-UP AND HANDLING OF PREFORMS FOR CFRP-FRAMES

Besides handling of CFRP-material for window frames and stringers the automated handling or draping of frame preforms is another aspect of an industrial production of CFRP-parts. For the production of frames a robot supported end-effector was developed to lay-up the dry preforms on a preform tooling. As a demonstration part a CFRP-frame with 2,5 m length and variable width was used to develop a modular and flexible end-effector. Figure 7 shows the contour of the CFRP-frame as a test part for testing different manufacturing processes. The robotic handling unit is adapted to the U-form.

Figure 7: CFRP-test frame for automated lay-up of the preforms

In general the preforms are being manufactured separately and joined in one cavity with resin. As a starting point the tape can be delivered on reels with binder, which can be activated by the influence of heat. The demands towards a robotic handling unit are the following:

- independent pick up of CFRP-reels
- independent feed of tape to the drape unit
- activating binder on the material
- form material (with active binder)
- cut material in length
- cut material in width at the preform core

Therefore an end-effector was developed, which can be guided by an industrial robot and has a certain connection through a base plate and a standard flange to supply the end-effector with power and signal communication with the robot control. The end-effector is also equipped with a drive unit, which can pick up the configured CFRP-reels, fix them on the end-effector and provide an automatic transport of the material across guide-plates and feed units at a defined speed. The feed unit is connected with the robot control to synchronize the speed of the tape in dependence to the robot's moving speed in order to ensure a slip-free draping process.

For activating the binder, a heating unit is installed. An ultra sonic cutter device provides the length definition of the material for the preform. To form the material across the preforming core a specially developed drape unit with a certain configuration of draping rolls was developed. In several draping tests the pressure for forming the tape across the preform core was defined and in the following the way of pressing the draping rolls. The end-effector and the configuration of the system assisted by the industrial robot is shown in the next figure 8.

Figure 8: End-effector for CFRP-frame preform lay-up

After realising the end-effector the programming of the system and the robot was completed. For the automatic lay-up of the CFRP-preform for frame preforms a peripheral control system was developed, which has to communicate with the robot control. Thus the programming and the teaching of the robot and the end-effector systems were developed.

The experiments have shown the complexity of the system. Initial results of the test have shown the potential of the system for automatic draping CFRP-preforms for frames.

OUTLOOK ON AUTOMATED HANDLING AND DRAPING OF CFRP-MATERIAL

The automated handling and draping of CFRP-material has to be developed for cost effective manufacturing of CFRP-parts in different industrial areas. The validation of different systems will show the high potential of automation. The repeatability of automatic systems will ensure a matured process with a high level of automation for high production rates of different parts in aerospace industry. Due to further projects we have had the near past, the automatic handling, draping and positioning of dry CFRP-fabrics and Prepreg-material is also very interesting for automobile industry, ship builders and wind energy industry.

CONCLUSION

This article has shown that the automated handling of dry fabrics and prepreg material is validated. Several tests and systems can handle different sorts of CFRP-materials with a very high level of repeatability and matured systems.

Both dry fabrics and prepreg material can be handled by special designed end-effectors. Further developments have been made with a very flexible system for handling different material geometries or different part geometries.

In addition, the extraction and deforming of stringer laminates were developed with a fully automated system being independent of manual processes. In further steps the positioning of the stringer laminates in the preforming tooling and following the positioning of the preformed stringer in the curing tooling has been developed. Thus the process chain of manufacturing CFRP-stringer can be performed by a fully automated system.

In another development a fully automated system for laying-up and draping CFRP-material across preform cores for manufacturing frame preforms was generated. This can lead to a cost effective and automatic system for manufacturing complex CFRP-frames for high rates in aero structure industry.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work has been carried out during two years of cooperation with universities of applied sciences and their students. Most input and work has been generated by our development engineers (i.e. Marcel Czaya and Thorsten Flessner) at Premium AEROTEC plant in Varel, Germany, at the Centre of Production Systems. Many Thanks to their engagement and time for realizing these systems